

Seed Testing Techniques for Genetically Modified Organisms (GMOs)

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Abstract

With the development of modern biotechnology, numerous GMOs have been approved for commercial production. Specially, some unauthorized or unknown GMOs are possibly present in the market owing to unintentional release of seed lots with unauthorized GMOs. Demands for testing GMO foods and development of reliable GMO analytical methods have been dramatically increasing. For this reason, many countries especially those in EU have recently issued restricted safety rules for import of GM foods. In this review article most useful GMO detection techniques are mentioned which will be ease the process of GMO detection such as Lateral Flow strips and CRISPR/cas12 based techniques (Wang *et al.*, 2022) will be found more realistic and less time consuming there is need to do research in that way this review article will help to understand those techniques.

Key words: GMO's, Seed testing, Analytical, ELISA, Lateral Flow Strips, Techniques, Detection

Introduction

GMO is as an organism in which the genetic material has been altered in a way that does not occur naturally by mating and/or natural recombination. It is done using advanced biology and technology which improve certain traits or characteristics such as increased yield, pest resistance and improved nutritional content. In India, the GM crop (*Bt* cotton) cultivation area covers 11.4 million hectares. The International Seed Testing Association (ISTA) is an independent, non-profit organization founded during the 4th International Seed Testing Congress in 1924. It involved in the development of internationally approved ISTA Rules for sampling and testing seed quality, laboratory accreditation and the promotion of seed science research and test development. The ISTA Rules, chapter 19 describes GM

seed testing protocols. It is conducting PT (Proficiency Tests) twice a year for GMO testing harmonization. In India ICAR-Central Institute of Cotton Research (CICR), Nagpur act as a referral laboratory for *Bacillus thuringiensis* cotton seeds (*Bt* cotton seeds) testing. It declared as the Central Seed Laboratory to detect presence or absence of *Bt* gene in cotton seeds in exercise of the powers conferred by Sub-section (1) of Section 4 of the Seeds Act, 1966 (54 of 1966). This institute developed ELISA and Lateral Flow Dipsticks (LFD) for *Bt* cotton seed testing. In this review article we will find out traditional and modern techniques for GMO seed testing.

GM seed testing techniques: it includes (1.) Protein based method and (2.) DNA based method

Figure: 1 flow chart GMO seed testing procedure

1. Protein based method

The most common protein-based assays are immunoassays: the target proteins are detected by specific monoclonal or polyclonal antibodies followed by immunochemical analysis (Micheleni et al. 2008). The Lateral flow devices(LFD) and plate-based enzyme-linked immunosorbent assays(ELISA) are the most widely used methods (Fantozzi et al.2007; Shim et al. 2007). Multiplex protein detection using immunological methods can be also achieved using microarray formats or flow cytometry by coloured beads coated with antibodies (Fantozzi et al. 2007; Ling et al. 2007). In order to increase the sensitivity of immunoassays, Allen et al. (2006)developed a novel immunoassay method in combination with PCR amplification. A sandwich enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (S-ELISA) method for the pat and bar genes in GM pep-per was developed, showing a detection limit of 0.01 µg/mL in real samples examination (Shim et al. 2007). Other alternative protein-based methods include the use of immunomagnetic electrochemical sensors, 2-dimensional gel electrophoresis, and mass spectrometry

(Kim et al. 2006; Volpe et al. 2006; Ocana et al. 2007). However, protein-based methods are not suitable for processed foods because of denaturation occurring during processing. In addition, the higher costs for developing specific antibodies and the fact that antibodies cannot be synthesized simply in comparison to oligonucleotides limits the method's evolution. Standardization of Testing Methods for GMOs to date, up to 184 kinds of events have been developed and approved for application in 59 countries worldwide (James 2011), and many countries have issued GMO labeling and traceability policies. With the quick development of economic globalization and international trade, much effort was taken to develop standard methods for GMO detection to reduce national and international trade disputes. Some organizations, such as International Organization for Standardization (ISO), the Community Reference Laboratory for GM Food and Feed (CRL-GMFF), and Standardization Committee for Agricultural GMOs of China have made significant efforts to initiate the validation and standardization of GMO testing methods. ISO provides some international standard for GMO sampling, DNA extraction, and PCR detection. In the EU, CRL-GMFF and others have also organized some deliberate collaborative ring trials for p35S and tNOS quantitative detection methods (Feinberg *et al.* 2005; Fernandez *et al.* 2005; Waiblinger *et al.* 2007) and event-specific. (Rupula *et al.*, 2021) standardized immuno-analytical method for the detection and estimation of transgenic *Cry1Ac* protein. Sandwich ELISA detected *Cry1Ac* protein with limit of 0.47ng. The developed method was validated in the screening of *Bt*, non-*Bt* biological seed samples and in germinating seedlings.

Figure: 2 Different models of ELISA techniques

Currently, the detection of GM crops is mainly based on protein assays, such as enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) (Zhang *et al.*, 2016) and immunochromatography assay (ICA) (Dou *et al.*, 2019) or DNA assays, including qualitative PCR (qPCR) and droplet digital PCR (dd PCR) (Wang, Chen, Li, Wang, & Liu, 2018). However, protein-based methods are not suitable for processed products with low GM content due to their limited sensitivity, while nucleic acid-based methods are mostly expensive, labour-intensive, and unsuitable for in situ tests.

The development of thermostatic nucleic acid amplification has become an irreversible trend in view of the demand for on-site detection. Many RPA-based methods have been established, such as RPA-AGE, RPA-ELISA (Yang et al., 2016), real-time RPA and RPA-LFD (Liu, Wang, Li, et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2020). The RPA reaction could be performed at 37 °C and be easily implemented in an outdoor environment. However, the sensitivity of the RPA method is still inadequate, and the combination with other techniques is an effective solution. Since the discovery of the *trans*-cleavage activity of Cas12a, CRISPR-Cas12a has recently been used for DNA detection with Atto molar sensitivity. Lateral flow strip test is based on immunoassay which uses a capillary paper which is immobilized with antibodies. Crude extract of seed is taken as a sample. Antigen in the extract binds with antibodies labelled with colloidal gold on the dipstick to form a distinct coloured band whenever antigen-antibody binds to each other. It is a qualitative rapid visual test and has been widely used for regulation of *Bt* cotton seed marketing in India. Immune Chromatographic Strip (ICS) for simultaneous detection of multiple transgenic proteins, including CP4 EPSPS, *Bt-Cry1Ab* and *Bt-Cry1Ac*. The sensitivity of the strip to the target protein was 5ng/ml for CP4 EPSPS, 100ng/ml for *Bt-Cry1Ab* and *Cry1Ac*, respectively. Maize, soybean, sugar beet and cotton detected 1% of transgenic content of *Bt-Cry1Ab* and *Cry1Ac* and at least, 0.1% of content in crops containing CP4 EPSPS was developed by (Zenga et al., 2021). (Wang et al., 2022) developed method based on Recombinase Polymerase Amplification, CRISPR/ Cas12a system and Lateral flow strip technology (RPA-Cas12a-LFB) for the rapid detection of Genetically Modified (GM) crops by targeting P-CaMV 35S and T-nos screening elements. This method detected 0.01% GM content of *Bt11* and MON863 samples which can be completed within 40 minutes.

Figure: 3 Schematic presentation of Lateral flow strip working way

2. DNA based Analytical method

Quantitative PCR based detection

To detect GMOs, qualitative PCR technologies are mainly used to screen and/or identify single or multiple transgenic DNA fragments, including single plex PCR, multiplex PCR, and nested PCR etc. In multiplex PCR, several primer pairs are included to permit the simultaneous detection of multiple target sequences. Generally, the qualitative PCR products are distinguished by size in agarose gel electrophoresis. Randhawa et al. (2009) developed a multiplex PCR assay with six marker/reporter genes (aadA, bar, hpt, nptII, pat, and uidA) that have already been introduced into GMOs. This assay could be immensely used to test unintentional mixing of GM seeds with non-GM seed lots. Onishi et al. (2005) reported respectively applications of multiplex PCR assay for simultaneous detection of up to eight events of GM maize and endogenous reference gene (zSSIIb or zein) within a single reaction. The limits of detection (LODs) were approximately 0.25% in both assays. However, the sensitivity and resolution are limited in agarose gel electrophoresis: the requirement of amplicons with apparent differences in size and the longer separation time. Recently, the combination of PCR and capillary gel electrophoresis (CGE) was developed for simultaneous detection of multiple DNA targets. The CGE assay accomplishes higher resolutions compared with agarose gel electrophoresis, and the sample separation time in the assay is shorter. Additionally, this assay has sensitivity and the reproducibility similar to real-time PCR (RT-PCR) (Nadal et al. 2006, 2009) and might be the most prospective analytical method for GMO detection. Nadal et al. (2009) presented the development of the CGE technology for the simultaneous detection of up to eight amplicons. The application offers an alternative tool for routine GMO identification. Guo et al. (2011) developed a robust high-throughput analytical approach named multiplex micro-droplet PCR implemented capillary gel electrophoresis (MPIC) (Figure 2). This assay combines the advantages of bipartite primers, microdroplet PCR and CGE for multiple target DNA analysis, and at least 24 different targets can be simultaneously detected and identified. Furthermore, the microarray is a reliable method for amplicon analysis, but it is also time-consuming and costly (Leimanis et al. 2006; Xu et al. 2007). Another alternative is application of combinations of screening methods and matrix table (Table 3), forming the basis of decision tools to conclude which GMP is present in a sample (Holst-Jensen 2009, Querci et al. 2010).

Figure 4: Real-time PCR

Qualitative PCR based detection

Generally, the purpose of GMO quantification is to calculate the fraction of a certain species that comes from GM materials relying on quantitative PCR (Buh Gasparic et al. 2010). In the quantitative PCR assay, the number of initial template molecules can be calculated based on the amount of the products through the standard curves. There are two specific targets needed in GMO quantification: reference gene sequence and exogenous gene sequence. The total number of taxon-specific haploid genomes and GM-specific haploid genomes that are present in the sample were estimated, respectively. The early quantitative PCR tests were based on double competitive PCR (DC-PCR), but quantitative real-time PCR (qRT-PCR), representing the most powerful current means of Quantifying GM ingredients, is the most widely used method for GMO detection (Buh Gasparic et al. 2008). Real time-PCR allows for the real-time monitoring of amplification reaction through fluorescence signal corresponding to increased amounts of amplification products at each reaction cycle. Because of its ease of use, high throughput ability, decreased post-PCR manipulation, and lack of cross-contamination of PCR amplicons, the RT-PCR method is becoming the new gold standard method for nucleic acid quantification (Yang et al. 2008b). Currently, several RT-PCR fluorogenic signal reagents have been developed and applied for quantitative purposes (Buh Gasparic et al. 2008,2010). Yang *et al* (2008b) reported a novel set of fluorescent signal device name Attached Universal Duplex Probes (AUDP), that can not only be used for different target DNA sequences in single PCR assays, but also in duplex PCR assays with higher fluorescence intensity. Moreover, amplified target DNA fragments as long as 1.5 kb can be detected with high efficiency.

DNA biosensors

Biosensor technology has been applied in a variety of molecular reactions including protein- and DNA-based testing, showing the advantages of simplicity, speed and cost (Elenis et al. 2008; Holst-Jensen 2009). For DNA biosensor technology, the single-stranded specific oligonucleotide probes (recognition layer) used as capture probes attached to the surface of the sensor is the most widely used. Other DNA biosensor methods based on optical, electrochemical, and piezoelectric transduction have been reported for the detection of amplified or non-amplified GMO-related sequences (Stobiecka et al. 2007; Ahmed et al. 2009; Bai et al. 2010). Surface plasmon resonance (SPR) is the typical optical biosensors-based method. (Gambari and Feriotto 2006) reported the SPR-based assay for rapid (about 40 min), easy, and automatable analysis of GM Roundup Ready soybean in foods. The hybridization of the target DNA with capture probe attached to the surface results in a change in the refractive index of the solution near the surface and shows a linear relationship to the mass of target DNA hybridized. Enzyme-based electrochemical sensors were developed using disposable oligonucleotide-modified

screen-printed gold electrodes. A probe carrying an -SH group at the 5'-end is attached to the gold surface. After the PCR product being denatured is hybridized with a biotinylated probe in solution, the solution is then pipetted onto the electrode and allowed to hybridize with the immobilized probe. The sensor is washed, and a streptavidin-alkaline phosphatase conjugate is added. The enzyme catalyses the hydrolysis of naphthyl phosphate substrate to the electro active naphthol, which is then detected by differential pulse voltammetry (Lucarelli et al. 2005).

Conclusion

Demands for testing GMO foods and development of reliable GMO analytical methods have been dramatically increasing, to understand the difference between GM and non-GM seeds these techniques can be very helpful and develop new technologies which will be reliable at farmer's field. ELISA methodology may find applications in agricultural laboratories to assess the *Bt* toxin content in the seeds provided to the farmers and in the commercialization of GMO crops additionally there is need to create awareness about IRM strategy for GMOs.

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